

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of DL-methionine by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of DL-methionine (Met) by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding sulfoxide. The reaction is of first order with respect to both TEACC and Met. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of methionine was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed by Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. Solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Keywords : Amino acid, halochromate, methionine, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Organic halochromates have long been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) is one such compound used for the oxidation of benzylic alcohols⁶. We have been interested in the kinetics of reactions of complexed Cr^{VI} species and have already reported kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation by other halochromates⁷⁻¹⁰. There seem to be no report on the oxidation of methionine by TEACC. Methionine (Met), a sulphur-containing essential amino acid, is reported to behave differently from other amino acids, towards many oxidants^{11,12}, due to electron-rich sulphur center which is easily oxidizable. Therefore, in continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation studies by halochromates, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of DL-methionine by TEACC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry :

The oxidation of methionine by TEACC resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxides. The overall reaction may therefore, be represented as eq. (1).

TEACC undergoes two electron change, which is accord to the earlier observation with structurally similar halochromates (PEC and PCC).

It has already been shown that both PFC¹³ and PCC¹⁴ act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies.

Rate laws :

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to TEACC. In individual kinetic runs, plots of log [TEACC] versus time were linear ($r^2 > 0.995$). Further, it was found that the observed rate constant, k_{obs} , does not depend on the initial concentration of TEACC. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of methionine (Table 1). Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile :

The oxidation of Met, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by TEACC at 308 K

10^3 [TEACC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Met] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	3.72
1.00	0.20	0.00	7.68
1.00	0.40	0.00	15.6
1.00	0.60	0.00	23.4
1.00	0.80	0.00	30.6
1.00	1.00	0.00	37.8
2.00	0.20	0.00	8.01
4.00	0.20	0.00	6.66
6.00	0.20	0.00	7.29
8.00	0.20	0.00	8.28
1.00	0.40	0.00	17.1 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of DL-methionine by TEACC : A typical kinetic run.

of oxidation (Table 1). Therefore, a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. We further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of acidity :

The reaction was studied at different acidities by adding varying amount of toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) to the reaction mixtures. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 2), The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The values of *a* and *b*

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Met] 0.10 mol dm ⁻³ ; [TEACC] 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ ; Temp. 308 K [TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	4.32	5.13	6.48	7.92	9.18	10.8

are $3.65 \pm 0.07 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $7.07 \pm 0.11 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9991$).

Effect of temperature :

The rates of oxidation of Met was determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3). The log k_2 at different temperature is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for these oxidations.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of TEACC as (eq. (2)) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar halochromates.

Solvent effect :

The oxidation of Met was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of TEACC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values k_2 at 298 K for the oxidation of Met are recorded in Table 4.

The rate constants for oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of the solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship eq. (3) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁵.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + \alpha\alpha$$
 (3)

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of Met by TEACC

288 K	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)			ΔH^* (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^* ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	ΔG^* (kJ mol^{-1})
	298 K	308 K	318 K			
8.37	18.0	37.8	80.1	54.7 ± 0.7	-114 ± 2	88.6 ± 0.6

Fig. 2. Oxidation of DL-methionine by TEACC : Effect of temperature.

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of methionine by TEACC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s^{-1})	Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s^{-1})
Chloroform	75.8	Acetic acid	33.9
1,2-Dichloroethane	63.1	Cyclohexane	2.82
Dichloromethane	69.2	Toluene	15.8
DMSO	180	Acetophenone	83.2
Acetone	52.2	THF	27.5
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	107	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	38.0
Butanone	41.7	1,4-Dioxane	29.5
Nitrobenzene	79.4	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	19.1
Benzene	19.9	Carbon disulfide	8.91
Ethyl acetate	25.7		

bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (3), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below.

$$\log k_2 = -3.51 + 1.56 (\pm 0.17) \pi^* + 0.15 (\pm 0.14) \beta + 0.26 (\pm 0.13) \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8975; sd = 0.15; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.45 + 1.46 (\pm 0.18) \pi^* + 0.24 (\pm 0.14) \beta \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8450; sd = 0.17; n = 18; \psi = 0.42$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.40 + 1.52 (\pm 0.18) \pi^* \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8166; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.44$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.60 + 0.50 (\pm 0.32) \beta \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1308; sd = 0.39; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

Kamlet's¹⁵ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 88% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's¹⁶ criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. (4)). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 83% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁷ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents as well.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (8)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A+B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 1.15 (\pm 0.04) A + 1.45 (\pm 0.03) B - 3.70 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9948; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.74 (\pm 0.94) A - 2.70 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1836; sd = 0.39; n = 19; \psi = 0.93$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.37 (\pm 0.20) B - 3.33 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7244; sd = 0.23; n = 19; \psi = 0.54$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.35 \pm 0.05 (A + B) - 3.69 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9807; sd = 0.06; n = 19; \psi = 0.14$$

The rates of oxidation of methionine in different solvents show an excellent correlation with Swain's equation with both the cation- and anion-solvating powers playing significant roles, though the contribution of the cation-solvation is slightly more than that of the anion-solvation. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also ac-

counted for *ca.* 98% of the data. However, the correlations individually with *A* and *B* were poor. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 98% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5057$; $sd = 0.30$; $\psi = 0.72$).

The observed solvent effect points to a transition state more polar than the reactant state. Further, the rotation of a dipolar transition state, similar to those of S_N2 reactions is indicated by the major role of both anion- and cation-solvating powers. However, the solvent effect may also be explained assuming that the oxidant and the intermediate complex exist as ion-pair in non-polar solvent like cyclohexane and be considerably dissociate in more polar solvents.

Mechanism :

In view of the absence of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate it is unlikely that a

one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this oxidation reaction. The experimental results can be accounted for in terms of electrophilic oxygen transfer from TEACC to the methionine-sulphur via an intermediate complex (eq. (13)). Similar mechanisms has been suggested for oxidation of sulfides and iodide ions by periodate ion¹⁸ and for the oxidation of sulfides by hydrogen peroxide¹⁹. The electrophilic attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 like transition state is supported by observed solvent effect also.

The oxidation of methionine by TEACC may involve a cyclic intermediate as has been suggested in many reactions of Cr^{VI} ²⁰. The cyclic transition state will be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone pair of electrons or an alky group (eq. (14)). The formation of a cyclic transition state entails a more exacting specificity of orientation and should result in much larger negative entropy of activation than that observed.

Experimental

Materials :

TEACC was prepared by the reported method⁶ and its purity checked by an iodometric method. Methionime (Merck) was used as supply. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ion. Other solvents were purified by the usual methods²¹.

Product analysis :

Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met by TEACC resulted in the formation of corresponding sulphoxide, which was determined by the reported method²². The yield of sulphoxide was $94 \pm 3\%$. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures i.e. after >10 half-lives, as determined iodometrically, was +4.

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of the Met over TEACC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [TEACC] spectrophotometrically at 370 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of \log [TEACC] against time for up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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